

Interview Guideline ‘On Observability and Monitoring of Distributed Systems’

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April 2019

Motivation

1. Please explain your product (software/service/process).
2. What is your recent position/role in the company?
3. What are your goals/purpose for the monitoring?
4. Do you have a service-description/service-level?
 - a. How do you define the service description/service-level? (Top-down, bottom-up?)

Requirements and Implementation Process

5. Which requirements are important for your monitoring concept?
6. Can you please describe the realization of implementing the monitoring concept?

Monitoring Solution

7. Which monitoring tool do you use?
8. Can you explain the most important criteria for the selection?
9. Which components do you monitor? What is the abstraction-level?
10. What is your approach for collecting the data?
11. Do you have all required data? Are the data available in real-time?
12. How do process the collected data?

Operated Monitoring Process and Strategy

13. Can you please describe the monitoring process in your daily work?
14. Do you have a defined process for troubleshooting?
15. How do you set your thresholds for the alerts?
16. How are you able to monitor the rapidly changing dynamic infrastructure?
17. Does your company has a monitoring strategy and governance?
18. How do you monitor third party services?

Lessons Learned, Challenges and Outlook

19. What are your lessons learned in monitoring distributed systems?
20. What challenges do you have in monitoring your distributed system?
21. Do you have plans for further developing the monitoring? How do they look like?
22. Where do you expect to optimization in the monitoring of distributed systems?
23. Where do you think are possibilities to use artificial intelligence for monitoring?